

Analyzing the growth of XLPE Insulation Damage Under the Application of Repeated Lightning Impulses Using Nonlinear Models

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Abstract: The most commonly used insulation systems in submarine cables and substations nowadays are cross-linked polyethylene(XLPE). The expected life of this insulation is reduced due to the phenomenon called treeing. The reduction in life of the insulation is mainly due to the overvoltage stresses such as lightning strokes affecting the insulation. The growth characteristics of trees under repeated lightning impulses are investigated using simulation-based nonlinear models in this work. After solving Poisson's equations for the required geometry of the XLPE insulation, the electric field values obtained are utilized to model the growth characteristics. Repeated lightning impulses are applied as the input to the model. The assessment of the damage is made by making use of the COMSOL-MATLAB Live link facility. The growth of the tree in the insulation is analyzed by developing a program based on a probabilistic approach. From the results, the analysis of the key parameters of insulation damage is done by histogram plots.

Keywords: Dielectric breakdown; Electric fields; Gas-insulated substations; Impulse testing, Lightning; Materials testing; Polyethylene insulation; Prediction methods; Cellular automata; Trees (insulation).

1 Introduction

Cross-linked polyethylene (XLPE) is the most commonly used insulating material in underground cables of ordinary substations, gas-insulated substations, and submarine cables due to its excellent electrical, thermal, physical properties, moisture and flame resistance, resistance to crushing and heat deformation. Despite the above-stated advantages, there are chances of getting damage to the insulation by a phenomenon called treeing. If a point defect or a void is present in the insulation, that part of the insulation gets overstressed as the field intensity at that point becomes very high

compared to other parts. As a result, insulation damage starts at the point and the phenomenon which is known as treeing is observed as the major cause of XLPE solid insulation failure before the expected lifetime of insulation. Damage caused to the insulation due to treeing depends upon many factors such as magnitude and frequency of the AC voltage striking the insulation, magnitude, and number of pulses striking the insulation in the case of impulse overvoltages. Different types of electrical trees found in the literature are tree-like trees, bush branch trees, bush trees, impulse trees, and fibrillar trees [1]. Gas Insulated substations(GIS) are becoming popular nowadays and it is reported that the major cause of failure in GIS is insulation failures. Overvoltages in such substations vary in the range from lightning overvoltages to fast-fronted overvoltages. When the cable insulation system in these substations is subjected to repeated impulses, failure may occur in the form of trees. Moreover, it is very important to assess the performance of the insulation in terms of the number of pulses that strike the insulation [2]. Hence a model for impulse trees formed in XLPE under repeated lightning impulses has been developed in this work.

Treeing phenomena are mainly investigated by two methods: empirical methods and simulation-based methods. One of the main tests that are conducted on insulation to assess its performance is the breakdown test. In XLPE treeing tests are also conducted and the importance has been mentioned in [3]. A detailed analysis of the insulation damage under both polarities of DC voltage has been done in [4]. An improvement in the properties of XLPE has been achieved in [5]. A new method for estimating the life of dielectrics has been introduced in [6]. The development of partial discharge in highly stressed areas of solid insulation has been the major cause of failure in solid insulation. The influence of partial discharges for the growth of electrical trees under the application of composite AC and DC voltages has been analyzed in [7]. The main parameters that

have been used to analyze the growth characteristics of electrical trees are tree length, width, and fractal dimension. These parameters under the application of AC voltage have been analyzed experimentally by the authors in [8]. In [9], the authors have developed a physical model to describe the breakdown phenomena in extruded polymers. The above analysis has been carried out by conducting actual experiments on the specimen. Simulation models are also equally important since real-world problems can be solved more securely and competently. Hence simulation modeling has been broadly accepted as it provides a good platform to address complex systems. Some of the existing simulation models developed so far by researchers in XLPE are described in the following paragraph.

A stochastic model to represent the breakdown in the form of narrow discharge channels has been developed in [10] and it is considered as one of the primary simulation models developed. In [11], a probabilistic model for different magnitudes of AC voltage applied to the dielectric material had been developed and experimentally evaluated. The energy released due to partial discharge in the material has been considered to develop a self-consistent model in the work[12]. A cellular automata model for treeing under DC voltage has been developed in [13]. After conducting an extensive review of existing models, the authors had developed an improved physical-stochastic model [14]. In [15], the authors had investigated the stationary electric field stress in HVDC cable joint interfaces. In

From the above literature review to the best of our knowledge, a simulation model to analyze the propagation characteristics of electrical trees in XLPE insulation under repeated lightning impulses does not exist. Hence, a suitable model has been developed in this work, for finding the growth features of electrical trees under repeated lightning impulse overvoltages in XLPE insulation. Poisson's equations have been solved across the insulating material to assess the characteristics of damage under lightning overvoltages. COMSOL multiphysics has been found very useful in many engineering applications for effectively solving many problems [16] including the solution of Laplace or Poisson's equations, for any geometry and under time-varying inputs in a competent way and hence is used in the present work. The field distribution values obtained after solving Poisson's

equation have been made use to develop a MATLAB code to find the propagation characteristics of the electrical tree. The COMSOL-MATLAB Live link facility has been used to obtain complete modeling of the phenomena.

The main contributions of our work are,

1. Modelling of the tree propagation characteristics by a probability-based approach using COMSOL-MATLAB Live link facility under repeated lightning overvoltages.
2. Analysis of the results by a histogram-based approach from a large number of samples.
3. Obtaining the parameters of the tree propagation under repetitive pulses applied to the insulation.

2 Materials and Methods

The following steps are involved in the development of the model to assess the propagation characteristics of insulation under repetitive impulse overvoltages. A 2D model of the XLPE insulation material and electrode geometry has been created first. Treeing experiments are usually carried out in insulation specimens of 10mm thick and by inserting a needle at a distance of 3-5mm from the bottom electrode. By doing this, trees are generated faster in the samples and make the analysis easy. To represent the actual experiments, the same dimensions of the sample as in experimental analysis have been modeled. After applying repeated lightning impulses as the input to the model created, Poisson's equation has been solved. From the solution matrix obtained, the propagation path of the trees has been visualized by a program. The parameters of treeing have been analyzed by a histogram-based approach. The above steps are repeated for the different numbers of pulses as inputs and the results have been verified. As treeing is a probabilistic phenomenon, 5000 samples have been analyzed in each case. These steps are described in detail in the subsequent sections.

2.1 Creating the model of XLPE insulation

A two-dimensional model of the XLPE sample specimen has been created in COMSOL software. The 2-dimensional geometry created was of dimension 10mm × 8mm rectangle to represent the actual experimental conditions. A needle of the tip of radius 5 μ m has been modeled and has been

inserted into the rectangular geometric sample at a distance of 3mm from the bottom electrode. The dielectric material has been given the properties of XLPE with a permittivity(ϵ_r) of 2.3, which is found in XLPE cable insulations. The needle has been inserted to create high stress to accelerate treeing phenomena while conducting actual experiments. The material usually used is copper and hence the modeled needle has been given the properties of copper. Ground boundary condition has been applied to the bottom electrode and repeated lightning impulses of magnitude 80kV have been applied to the top electrode. Simulations have been carried out with 2 repeated impulses and the results have been analyzed in each case. Equations solved at different boundaries are described below.

Under the charge conservation node, Poisson's equation given by Equation (1) has been solved

$$\nabla \cdot \epsilon_0 \epsilon_r E = \rho \quad (1)$$

A time-dependent solver has been chosen to solve the equation. Ground boundary condition has been assigned to the bottom electrode and Equation (2) has been solved.

$$V = 0 \quad (2)$$

Lightning impulses applied were of the standard impulse of front and tail 1.2/50 μ s as shown in Equation (3) (IS-20171)

$$u(t) = A(e^{-\alpha t} - e^{-\beta t}) \quad (3)$$

Here, $u(t)$ is the instantaneous magnitude of the wave, A is the amplitude, α and β are respectively the reciprocal of wave tail and wavefront constant. A triangular mesh of extremely fine quality has been chosen for the elements in the geometry to improve accuracy.

2.2 Assessment of the propagation path of electrical tree

The experimental methods for the assessment of impulse tree characteristics have been found in [17]–[19]. Since voltages such as lightning impulse overvoltages are having large values in practice, these experiments are subjected to limitations. However, to investigate the characteristics of propagation, the experimental method is found useful. Because of these facts, several simulation

models had been developed. It should be mentioned here that all the developed models to date have been found suitable for AC voltages and not for impulse voltages or repeated impulse voltages. Considering these facts, we have tried to fill this gap by developing a simulation model for impulse trees under 2 repeated impulses. It is worth here to mention here that to the best of our knowledge, it is the first attempt to model an impulse tree growth in XLPE polymeric insulation under repeated lightning impulses.

To start the tree initiation, the electric field intensity should exceed a critical value(E_{max}) which depends upon the applied voltage, the radius of the electrode, and the distance between the top and bottom electrode, and this is governed by Equation (4).

$$E_{max} = \frac{2V}{r \ln\left(1 + \frac{4d}{r}\right)} \quad (4)$$

Where E_{max} is the extreme electric field strength, V the applied input voltage at the tip of the needle. The needle tip radius is represented by r and the space between the needle tip to the ground electrode is denoted by d .

When the strength of the electrical field reaches a critical value called critical field strength(E_c) of 4MV cm^{-1} , the value of electric stress overcomes the mechanical stress, and a tree is initiated [20]. Treeing has been considered as a stochastic phenomenon and hence the tree growth under repeated lightning impulses has been modeled based on a probabilistic approach.

The method adopted in our work involves the following steps.

Step 1. A 2D model of the insulating material with required dimensions has been created in COMSOL multiphysics as described in subsection 2.1.

Step 2. Lightning impulse waveform input is a standard impulse of specifications mentioned in section 2.1

Step 3. After solving Poisson's equation, the solution matrix has been extracted as the electric field intensity matrices at each node points in the material. A time-dependent solver had been chosen with a total of 50-time steps. Since the tree initiation starts from the tip of the needle only, which is 3mm from the bottom electrode, the solution matrix

considered was only for the dimensions $8mm \times 3mm$. The solution matrix extracted consists of a grid of dimensions 120x321(rows and columns) which represents the XLPE specimen.

Step 4. Starting from the tip of the needle, each cell of the solution matrix has been assessed for the following conditions: (a) if any of the neighboring cells is identified as a tree, the value of the local field intensity of the cell is checked for the criticality condition of the electrical field (b) If the criticality condition is satisfied, a random number(p , refers here as the probability condition) is sampled from a normal distribution and if $p > 0$, that cell has been added to the existing tree cell. If either criticality condition or probability condition is not satisfied, that cell has been allowed to continue in the present state. The algorithm for the propagation of the tree has been written as a MATLAB function. The algorithm developed, can be considered similar to the cellular automata model [13] with some modifications. We have used COMSOL–MATLAB Live link for the complete simulation where, in each iteration or time step, the solution matrices had been taken from COMSOL and the growth of the tree has been modeled in MATLAB. The flow chart of the algorithm for the program developed is shown in Fig. 1.

3 Results and discussions

3.1 Formulation of the algorithm

The formation and propagation of electrical trees under the influence of repeated lightning impulses have been investigated. The solution matrix consisting of the electric field intensity values has been used to develop a program to study the tree propagation characteristics such as length and width when repeated impulses are applied to the insulating material. A time-dependent study has been carried out and the sample plot of field distribution obtained at one-time step is shown in Fig. 2. It can be observed that the tip of the needle has maximum intensity as indicated by the red color. As the initiation of the damage starts from the tip of the needle, the electric field values below the needle are of great importance to assess the propagation characteristics. The change in the solution matrix of the electric field intensity below this region has been considered at different time intervals.

From the solution matrix, it is also observed that the E field values decrease towards the bottom ground electrode. As the value changes in each time step, there is a chance of more and more cells in each row getting converted into a tree cell. This is based on the criticality condition and a probability condition. It should be noted here that, in simulations based on the stochastic phenomenon, the dimensions of the generated structure vary in each iteration, and hence several simulations need to be carried out for analyzing the results.

Fig. 1. Flowchart of the algorithm for the modeling of impulse tree propagation: A probabilistic model has been used to generate the tree

Fig. 2 Electric field distribution over the insulator surface: Complete block represents the XLPE specimen and the copper electrode is placed at a distance of 3mm from the bottom(ground) electrode. 80kV impulse voltage has been applied to the top electrode. The tip of the needle is found stressed most and the intensity variation can be seen varying from blue color representing lowest field intensity value to red color representing highest field intensity value. The field intensity is maximum at the tip of the electrode

Because of this, 5000 simulations have been carried out in each case of applied impulses. The parameters obtained after each simulation have been stored after each iteration to analyze later. The sample plot of the tree obtained in one among 5000 iterations is presented in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3 Electrical tree growth under repeated standard lightning impulse overvoltage: Figure shows one sample plot of the tree growing out of the 5000 different samples of simulations. It can be seen that the tree starts from the middle of the top electrode where the electrode is placed and propagates towards the bottom(ground) electrode

3.2 Assessment of the parameters of the tree

Electrical trees are usually distinguished by their parameters such as length, and width [8], [21], [22].

The change in these parameters at each of the time steps has been investigated next for impulses applied as the input. Each cell in the solution matrix corresponds to the geometric dimensions of the material. Hence the length has been assessed by a program that finds out the number of the last row that contains the tree flag. To assess the width of propagation, a similar program has been developed that finds out the difference in columns that contains a tree flag. In each iteration, the programs store the value in a matrix of the complete 5000 iterations.

The dimensions of the damage have been found to vary in each iteration of the simulation since the stochastic modeling approach is employed. It is worth here mentioning that treeing is a stochastic phenomenon and hence probabilistic approach is found appropriate. It may also be noted here that finding the mathematical average is also inappropriate to better represent the results. Hence, a histogram-based approach is adopted to analyze the results.

Table 1 shows the data used to generate the histogram plot for length. Each row in the table gives the range of values that the length has propagated. The x-axis values of the histogram denote the average value of each row in the table.

Fig. 4 shows the comparison of length obtained for 5000 iterations for the applied impulses. In the histogram plot, the x-axis represents the length of trees, and the y-axis represents the frequency of their occurrence in iterations. The data spread has been found to vary from 0.005 mm to 0.275 mm for the complete iterations. It is observed that data points representing the length of impulse trees are 0.005 in most of the iterations. Subsequent data points showed an exponential decay towards a larger length.

The histogram data has been further analyzed by fitting models to the data. Figs. 5 and 6 show the exponential and polynomial-law models applied to the length of propagation.

Table 1. This table presents the simulation outcome of 5000 observations for the length of propagation. Here L1 and L2 represent the lower and upper ranges of propagation length respectively in the 2D model, for studying the growth of the electrical tree in XLPE.

L1(mm)	L2(mm)	Frequency of occurrence
0	0.01	1733
0.02	0.03	985
0.05	0.06	601
0.07	0.08	481
0.1	0.11	315
0.12	0.13	232
0.15	0.16	176
0.17	0.18	121
0.2	0.21	80
0.22	0.23	73
0.25	0.26	71
0.27	0.28	132

Fig. 4 Histogram of the length of trees obtained for 5000 iterations: x-axis represents the length in mm for which the tree has propagated in each iteration and y-axis represents the frequency of occurrence for that particular length. More values show a tendency to fall in low values of length and fewer frequencies are observed for large lengths.

Fig. 6 Polynomial law fitted to the length of propagation

It can be observed that polynomial law fit is more appropriate marginally. Table 2 shows the data used to generate the histogram for width. Each row in the table gives the range of values that the width has propagated. The x-axis values of the histogram denote the average value of each row in the table.

Fig. 5 Exponential law fitted to the length of propagation

Table 2. This table presents the simulation outcome of 5000 observations for the width of propagation. Here W1 and W2 represent the lower and upper ranges of propagation width respectively in the 2D model, for studying the growth of the electrical tree in XLPE.

W1(mm)	W2(mm)	Frequency of occurrence
0	0.01	2038
0.02	0.03	1127
0.05	0.06	748
0.07	0.08	475
0.1	0.11	303
0.12	0.13	155
0.15	0.16	80
0.17	0.18	47
0.2	0.21	17

Fig. 7 shows the histogram representing the width of propagation for 5000 iterations. It can be observed that the data points for width vary from 0.005mm to 0.205mm during the complete iterations. A large number of samples have been observed for 0.005. The representation of the data points showed an exponential variation here also. Figs. 8 and 9 show the exponential and polynomial-law models applied for the width of propagation.

Fig. 7 Histogram of the width of trees obtained for 5000 iterations: x-axis represents the width in mm for which the tree has propagated in either direction from the center electrode in each iteration and y-axis represents the frequency of occurrence for that particular length. A similar variation like length is observed here also.

Fig. 8 Exponential law fitted to the width of propagation

Fig. 9 Polynomial-law fitted to the width of propagation

From the analysis, it is observed that polynomial distribution is more suitable in the case of width of propagation also. A comparison of different

nonlinear models applied to the histogram is shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Comparison between different models

Model	R ² (length)	R ² (Width)
Exponential law	0.8843	0.987
Power law	0.8863	0.7404
Logarithmic law	0.9808	0.9955
Polynomial(6 th degree)	0.9992	0.9985

R² is a statistical measure that shows how close the data are to be fitted on the regression line. The value lies between 0% and 100. 100% indicates that the model explains all the variability of the response data around its mean. Even though the different models show a small difference in the R² values, it can be observed that a polynomial distribution(6th degree) has been found better for both the length and width of the trees. All the simulations have been carried out on a PC with specifications: Intel(R) Core(TM) i3-7130U CPU @ 2.70GHz with RAM capacity 16GB. The total

simulation time for 5000 iterations was around 6 hours. From the values of length and width, it is also observed that the trees show a tendency to grow lengthwise compared to widthwise.

4 Conclusions

The effect of two repeated lightning over voltages in the propagation of electrical trees in XLPE insulation has been investigated. The investigation is conducted by obtaining the electric field intensity distribution throughout the specimen by solving Poisson's equations after applying repeated lightning impulses. As tree propagation is considered a probabilistic phenomenon, several simulations have been carried out for more accurate assessment. The results of 5000 iterations have been analyzed using a histogram-based approach. The propagation parameters of electrical trees such as tree length and width have been assessed by fitting nonlinear models to the data obtained. For the length and width of propagation under two repeated impulses, polynomial distribution has been found suitable with a marginal difference in R² values compared to other models. From the analysis, it is also observed that the growth of the trees is lengthwise compared to widthwise. The findings in the work will be useful in the design of the insulation system. The study can be extended to different insulating materials used in cables.

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